

Rilegno

National wood collection and recycling network

Italy's national consortium for the collection, recovery and recycling of wood packaging is a dynamic group of 2,000 companies, which transform wood, produce packaging, supply and import semi-finished packaging. The voluntary members include recycling companies, producers of boards, pulp, blocks, panels and pallets. The large network enables a competitive recycling market of up to 2 million tons of collected material annually.

Highlights of innovative features

- The collection network covers the entire territory with 419 private collection platforms serving the industrial and commercial sector.
- More than 4,500 municipalities representing over 42 million inhabitants have signed agreements for urban collection.
- 15 major panel producers recycle large volumes to supply board products to furniture and construction industries, amounting for about 3.2 million tons of released items.
- 63% of the material sent for recycling into boards comes mainly from wooden packaging such as pallets, crates for fruit and vegetables, boxes, cable reels, cork stoppers.
- In addition, 60 million items equal to 839,000 tons of regenerated pallets are returned to the market, which thus re-enter the logistics circuit instead of becoming waste.
- The gained CO₂ savings amount to around 1 million tons per year. The economic impact is around 1.4 million euros and 6,000 jobs.

The Rilegno network is a showcase of excellence in post-consumer wood waste and recycling logistics, maximizing the benefits of an integrated circular value chain and market approach for the entire wood and furniture sector.

Company | Ownership of innovation

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